

ESTIMATING AFFORESTATION OF GATWALA FOREST PARK DISTRICT FAISALABAD THROUGH SENTINEL-2 AND LANDSAT-5 IMAGERY

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Abstract

Forests are the main source from where we get our food/wood for our living. Growing forests help us to get a healthy environment. Plantation of trees in the area where there was no previous tree cover is known as Afforestation. Many governments and non-governmental organizations directly engage in programs of afforestation to create forests, increase carbon capture. The main objective of the study was to estimate the afforestation or deforestation land cover located in the district Faisalabad take place in the Gatwala Forest Park located in the Faisalabad district for the years 2000 and 2020. Results indicate about afforestation in the study area during 2000 and 2020. Vegetation land cover was increased from 56.97% to 62.01% and the Non-Vegetated area was decreased from 43.02% to 37.99%. Kappa coefficient performed to well access the classified imagery obtained from using the Sentinel-2 dataset, therefore, Sentinel-2 imagery proved more reliable in comparison to Landsat imagery. The spectral response of two land use classes were used in the research to recognize features through optical datasets. Results proved that sincere efforts of Ministry of Forestry in promotion of vegetated land cover. The coverage of Pakistan government must be enhanced for increasing vegetation for a green Pakistan.

Keywords: Afforestation, Gatwala Forest Park, Faisalabad, Sentinel-2, Landsat-5, NDVI, Supervised Classification, Kappa Coefficient, Remote Sensing, GIS

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Forest is an area of land dominated by trees. Forests are significant for natural and ecological processes. It is responsible for rains on the land. It also prevents soil erosion. Forests still cover 30% area of the earth land, but every year the average area of 75,625km² is lost (Faiza, Weiguo, Aijun, & Wenxing, 2017). Pakistan is a highly populated country in Asia with relatively less forest cover about 2.5% of its total land. Most of the country's forest is degraded, and recent deforestation reports indicate high prevalence of about 1.65% which was previously recorded at 0.6% during the period of 1981-1990 and 1.5% between 1991 and 2010. Forest area of Pakistan remains approx. 1.9% of the total land area, which is decreasing at an annual rate of 42,000 hectares (WB, 2017; Randhawa, 2017). Deforestation, desertification, and grassland degradation, among other reasons, have produced huge environmental disturbance, such as dust storms, wildlife habitat loss, reduced water resources and increased soil erosion. In addition, people's livelihood has also been affected badly, as shown by the prevalence of food insecurity and poverty, and a decrease in employment. a researcher asserts that every year in Pakistan 39,000 hectares of natural forest are disappearing. (Rauf, Khan et al. 2019) The world's forest area covered 30% of the global land area (3.8 billion hectares) in 2005 that has slightly increased to 31% (3.99 billion hectares) in 2015. Globally, over 1 billion people depend on forests for livelihood (FAO 2010; UNEF 2011a). Afforestation projects got momentum in developing countries especially during 1970s and 1980s (Michikazu et al., 1999). Afforestation projects got momentum in developing countries especially during 1970s and 1980s (Thomas et.,al 2010). In forestry sector, the global profile for the projects under CDM sets India at the top with 9 projects, China with 4 and Pakistan with no

projects. (Larson et.,al 2011). 2011 was considered "the international year of the forest" by the UN for sustainable forest management (Owais, Siddiqui, & Geology, 2019). The 21st century's dramatic changes in the climatic patterns became the biggest malice and severe threats to growth and development, yet alone human survival (Xie, He et al. 2017). Forests are the diverse environmental subjects, which have the capacity to adapt to the changes in the ecosystem and provide positive sustainable returns to the environment (Aljerf 2017). But there is great threat to forest cover und the broader domain of vegetative cover on the land surface and the main source is humans. human-induced activities remain the main causes behind the loss of forest cover, e.g., removal of forests and/or reduction in the capacity of the forests to serve as carbon sinks (Zhang, Ju et al. 2015). The other and the most severe reason behind the loss of forest cover and there-upon massive carbon release is the rapid urbanization (Bhatt and Urbanization 1990). Here, urbanization is amongst the critical factors affecting forest cover that is posing severe impacts on both regional and global environment (Lin, Qiu et al. 2019). The reported adverse impacts erosion, drought and loss of biodiversity (Huang, Kuo et al. 2016).

1.2 Problem Statement

Pakistan has less than 5% of forest cover over the total land area (Faiza et al., 2017). Deforestation is caused by agriculture expansion, population pressure, commodity and timber prices, wage levels, population growth, tourism, improvement of accessibility and increase of linkages between high and low lands, change in lifestyle and cultural patterns, opening to the external economies and global economic integration, external interventions in the form of development initiatives, and lack of governmental policies and high illegal harvesting activities (Rauf, Khan et al. 2019). In Pakistan, the rate of deforestation is estimated to be 1.5%. In 1990 according to the government of Pakistan, the rate of deforestation in the country is about to be the second-highest in the world (Faiza et al., 2017).

In 2010 official sources of Pakistan highly claimed that due to afforestation Pakistan's forests have been increasing progressively (Qasim, Hubacek, Termansen, & Khan, 2011). FAO's report claimed that the annual forest cover change rate during 1990-2000 was -1.8% and during 2000-2012 it was -2.2 (Qamer et al., 2012). The forest change detection can be calculated by GIS technology truly because it can handle both 'spatial' and 'a spatial' data (Ahmad et al., 2012). Change detection for GIS is a process that measures how the attributes of a particular area have changed between two or more periods (Zaib un Nisa1 & Batool2, 2018). It is useful in the assessment of deforestation.

Our atmosphere consists of different gases like oxygen, nitrogen, carbon dioxide and it is highly concentrated by greenhouse gases like methane and carbon dioxide which is due to deforestation that is a major factor of global warming (Dania Amjad1, 2019). The rate of carbon in the forest is higher than in other types of environments (KHAN, 2019).

Deforestation of forests area is a big problem for our government because the mainly rural population is dependent on these forest's wood (Qamer et al., 2012). Deforestation is the root cause of land degradation. Environment change and deforestation are directly proportional to each other.

Satellite images are very useful for both statistical and visual evaluation of natural resources and land cover change (Uddin et al., 2019). The remote Sensing technique is more accurate and useful. It provides large area coverage for calculating change detection and also for forest mapping (KHAN, 2019). The application of GIS & RS is in the mapping of different natural resources and spatial data modeling. It has been also used in single thematic analyses such as LULC mapping, forest monitoring, and forest fire management (Sajjad et al., 2015). Our area of interest is Gatwala Forest Park that is situated 17km of Faisalabad along Faisalabad-Sheikhupura Road and 120km away from Lahore. The rate of annual rainfall in Faisalabad was 615mm. In this study we use two types of datasets one is Landsat-5 and the other is sentinel -2 images for monitoring deforestation rate. Sentinel-2 provides images of high resolution (Anwar Ali 1, 2018). Air quality in Faisalabad is very unhealthy for breathing it is also due to the deforestation and pollution of industries.

1.3 Need of the Study

Pakistan has been consistently ranked among the ten countries worst affected by climate change. The increased frequency and intensity of extreme climate events during the last two decades in Pakistan, has had serious and long-term adverse impacts on the country. To bring the greenhouse gas emissions down to net zero and prevent a climate tipping point we need afforestation to tackle a problem that faces our country.

1.4 Aims & Objective

The major objectives of the study were:

- Calculate how much Afforestation happens in Gatwala Forest.
- Determine forest density rate between 2000 to 2020.
- Measure the factors that affect the forest by applying different analyses on software.

1.5 Study Area

Gatwala Forest Park (GFP) is located along 17km Faisalabad to Sheikhpura road, and it is situated near Khurrianwala and 140km away from Lahore Zoo, Punjab, Pakistan. It is the largest park in Faisalabad.

Gatwala Forest Park is a huge compound of more than 100km² that houses Forest areas, parks, lakes, and administrative buildings of the Ministry of Forestry. It was established in 1992. The latitude and Longitude of Gatwala are 31.4658°N and 73.1940°E. It covers an area of 131 acres. Almost the distance from Clock Tower, Faisalabad is 20km. The annual rainfall rate in this forest is 615mm. Almost all types of plants are available in this forest. Many types of herbaceous plants are also available in this Forest that is used for the treatment of common cold, sore throat, skin disorders, hepatic diseases, asthma, and joint pains. The hottest month is June with minimum and maximum temperature of 29°C to 43°C. The coldest month is December with minimum and maximum temperature of 19°C to 24°C.

Figure 1: Study area Map of Gatwala Forest Park

2. Review of Literature

(ULLAH, 2018) Estimate the success of plantation and evaluated the growth performance rate. Sentinel-2 images were used to calculate the vegetation and regression indices values. The output of that research showed good performance in term of survival rate. NDVI rate of landsat-8 2013 image & Sentinel-2 2018 image showed that it was increased from 0.68 to 0.85. (T. R. 1 et al., 2019) They Analyzed Billion Tree Afforestation Program (BTAP) and its effects on rural livelihoods, natural forests and decreased poverty rate in KPK. BTAP was a strongest measure for increasing livelihood assets and households earn 4% more income. (Waqar Ahmad, *, & Liaqat Ali Shah2), 2020) Conducted a study estimate the effects of vegetation on precipitation and air temperature in Pakistan. The value of NDVI varied from area to area e.g. Hilly and urban areas had different NDVI rate. The output of this study showed that the positive relationship exists between NDVI and precipitation and negative relationship between NDVI and air temperature. And also high rate of NDVI or afforestation reduced the climate change effect. (Khar11 & 2017) In future life, Pakistan will be facing the issue of climate change & environment degradation due to declined forests. This research reviewed the rate of environment degradation and analyzed BTTAP progress for environment sustainability. (Arshad Ashraf1, , & Muhammad Munir Ahmad, 2017) Study was associated with the issue of soil erosion. Soil erosion was a major issue that effected agriculture and water resource development in Himalaya region. Afforestation was a technique that reduced the risk of soil erosion and also constructed dams in sloppy areas that control soil erosion. (X. Z. 1 et al., 2018) said that for the sustainability of land we need to understand the changes in soil quality. Afforestation has the ability to increase the soil quality in china's loess Plateau. The soil bulk density and pH both were affected by stand age. Afforestation increased our harvesting rate. (OWOEYE1, , & NJUGUNA2, 2019) They adopted quantitative and qualitative research methods for the improvement of environment sustainability. Afforestation has the potential to increase the forest cover as well as improved food security and also provide a shelter to species for regeneration. For instance, the New Njukiri CFA in Embu West, Kirimari Ward planted 150,000 tree seedlings 75% exotic and 25% indigenous tree species, in 2 year (2015-2017). (IBRAHIM* & MUHAMMAD**, 2015) Nigeria has been devastated by many environmental problems which can be decrease through afforestation. Afforestation decreased the rate of deforestation, erosion and flooding as well as effects of climate change. This action increased the supply of forest products. (Maria Nijnik, 2011) Afforestation in Ukraine has increased the production of timber and prevented this land from erosion and climate mitigation. The output of this research showed that at discount rates lower than 2%.

(Danijel Beluši 2019) In some regions of Europe extra tropical cyclones were dominant over weather and cause precipitation. By using regional climate model and a cyclone tracking algorithm they measured how perfectly Deforestation & Afforestation affected the number of change in cyclones. The winter precipitation & cyclones were reduced with afforestation. (Qazi, 2016) Afforestation program was implemented by HJRA organization. In this agency trees was planted by techniques that reduced the risk of disaster. This effort increased the sustainability of environment conditions and provided good wild life habitat.

(Hussain, 2015) The nature, resource of food and livelihood security is different in mountain area than plain area. In mountain area, it was difficult to grow the crops because of the unbalanced land and lack of water. This analysis also provided different ways to faced many problems in mountain area. (Yue Li & Ling Huang, 2018) China was rapidly changed in dry land by evapotranspiration. It needed to plant more forest to remove the evapotranspiration that controlled the soil moisture. Minerals that affected the upper ground level, we should be overestimating these analyses that increasing the dry land than we should be able to control it.

(KATHLEEN A. FARLEY *w, 2005) The system of afforestation did not control the carbon system it also affect ecosystem and water yield. It was needed to overcome the deforestation in proper way. The result demonstrated that through the flow of water was controlled by the afforestation of grassland and scrubland. By the rate of deforestation percentage will be 1 by 3 than they controlled it. (Asif Kamal1, 2019) The Billion Tree Afforestation Project launched by government of KPK. In 2014, they were working on with rules and by laws. The development had basic effect on climate. This project controlled by Pakistan environment project act at 1997 to 2014 but it was provided benefit sequester for us in 2020.

(Berki et al., 2013) The forest and Afforestation was very important for at the last stage of life because the forest was controlled the atmosphere, dust storm and rock of stream and level of underground system. Ecologically conscious policy awarded present, further condition and consequence if not work on it. Forest is dry land that it was involved in continent.

(Lacombe et al., 2015) The humid tropic was increased by the deforestation that effects the environment. The Afforestation controlled the stream flow, availability of shelter, water resources and flood danger. The GR2M water balanced model gave successive result at area of Laos and Vietnam by the afforestation. We can remove the humid tropic by do more planting.

(Sarah Waseem, 2019) Vegetation cover was decreased and they cause carbon emission that also increased our environmental temperature. According to GIS and LST the vegetation cover increased in every year like 22% in 1992 to 2000 and 51% in 2008 to 2017. In this effort we needed to remove pollution and increased carbon sinks by Afforestation.

(NAZIRI*, FAROOQ2, JAN1, & AHMAD3, 2019) Plant billion tree, an afforestation project delivered in Pakistan province KP. Billion Tree Afforestation Project aimed to increase vegetative area and focused on a suitable land for afforestation. The projection of this project showed that the 3.29% increase in forest area instead of 2%. At the end of this project afforestation was not increased but deforestation was controlled.

{Masera, 2003} They used second version of CO2FIX (CO2FIX V.2) model for the estimation of carbon balance that was stored in the living or forest biomass and in soil. It plays important role for temperate & tropical conditions. The output of this research showed that temperate & tropical forest management system was presented.

(OMER, 2010) The experiment of Afforestation was taken at Alsalam and Abushouk internal Displaced campus that in north area during the Nov 2008 between April 2009. Thus it has taken the views of people by reporting field surveys, questioning and interviews. The people appreciated the good result and said there is need to do more work on afforestation in this area. (Keiffer, 1999) The Afforestation is important for human beings as well as species. Afforestation provided the shelter to species and also played important role for regeneration. The data proved that Afforestation was good for browsing with comparison in hardwood living species. (Maria Nijnika, 2012) Clean development mechanism (CDM) helped to identify the area or land which was beneficial for afforestation we will get two opinions by CDM first one was the availability of suitable land and the other was the development of community-based forestry. By both they focused on local livelihood and biodiversity.

{Suhadiyah1, 2014} They have needed to grow plants but also found suitable plants for healthy environment. They were two main cause of environmental pollution. First one was increased of traffic volume and other was deforestation. It was identified that there is no need to increase the trees in number but quality of plants was also important like stomata and trachoma that introduced in unhas campus.

(Yahya Kooch, 2012) Soil organic carbon sequestration has been directed affected by the afforestation. Four types of soil with different depth were used in this experiment (0-10, 10-20, 20-30, and 30-40). They were needed more planting but also the quality of plants was important that increased the SOCS on land.

(*Hakim Shah, 2010) Forest resources management used the usual techniques in mountain's area. District Kohistan and District Battagram of province PK were selected for this experiment. Multi Criteria Decision Analysis was used for site quality for afforestation. 42% land had potential for afforestation but 4% was recommended for dense afforestation. MCDA was identified and classified the area for afforestation.

(G.A.Thivakaran, 2017) Mangroves have a productive environment that was suitable for afforestation. The deforestation was less than -1%. In Gulf of Kachchh they used three methods for afforestation first one was transplantation of nursery raised sapling, second was plant were planted in lines and third was directly propagule dibbing. The transplantation technique of sapling was more successful because they solved the

issues of poor selection and poor technical skills could be more meaningful and productive for coastal communities.

{Ali, 2019} KPK has contained one-third forest area of the country's 4.5×10^6 . Carbon was presented in forest soil more than other land-use. It plays important role for our atmosphere. They estimated the soil organic carbon in the province by taking field-based study during 2014-17. The results of this study was estimated the quantity of SOC 59.4×10^6 . 69% of soil carbon presented in temporal forest.

{Paul, 2002} The large scale of afforestation has increased change in soil carbon. Different articles showed the variation in soil which was increased 0.50% and 0.86% per year. The carbon of soil was affected by previous land, climate and also the planation of Pinus radiant. The output of this research showed that C in soil has increased in upper layer of forest than the under preceding pasture.

{Gilliam's, 2005} Spatial Decision Support System (SDSS) and GIS software were used for the planning of decision & policies to get suitable agricultural land for afforestation. GIS has provided answers to queries by using Boolean operation. MCDM provided suitable location & techniques for afforestation. This paper compared three techniques PROMETHEE II was preferable than ELECIRE III and AHP due to user friendliness.

{Doelman, 2020} Afforestation was used to limit the climate change to 2°C or even 1.5°C and also have potential to reduce the risks in global mitigation policy & negative trade-off of food security by using IMAGE 3.0 integrated assessment model framework. Afforestation has faced many risks for the implementation. It also needed large amount of land that causes reduction in agriculture land. This action increased the food prices and risks of hunger.

{Laganiere, 2010} In the result of deforestation the stock of soil organic carbon was reduced. The afforestation had ability to increase SOC stock. They used meta-analysis for the restoration of SOC. The planation of broadleaf trees, pine species and demonstrated the clay-rich soil have ability to increased SOC.

{Nazir, 2017} A system dynamic model was used to estimate the level & impact of illegal wood harvesting. This paper collected the data from 1990-2010. The output of the research showed that illegal logging was 4 times greater than legal wood harvesting. The rate of illegal harvesting decreased by the increased of farmland wood supply.

{Ilstedt, 2007} They reviewed different studies on the effect of afforestation on infiltration in the tropics. By the process of erosion and infiltration the soil water was discharged in groundwater and loses the potential of upper soil. The meta-analysis was used to estimate the change it showed the rate of infiltration was increased on average three-fold after the increased of afforestation.

{Arora, 2011} The United Nation provided strategies for afforestation to mitigate the climate change. The afforestation also increased carbon sequestration. They used the Earth system model to estimating climate change mitigation. 50% afforestation of the area reduced warming around 0.45 and 0.25°C . The afforestation reduced the warming 4 times higher in tropics those temperate regions. That's why we have to need more afforestation in tropics for our environment.

{Boyd, 2007} The clean development mechanism worked on the small-scale sinks product for low-income communities. The investor has taken little interest in these types of projects because of the higher risks & uncertainties but economically, carbon has an ability to become popular in world market. This paper explored the adaptation of forest carbon project by highlighting the importance of local organization and rural development strategies.

{Allen, 2001} In Ireland they have planned to double the proportion of forest cover in 2035. They ignored their impacts on groundwater as 25% of population use groundwater for their needs. Field investigation was used to estimate that afforestation reduced the runoff as much as 20%. The capacity of forest soil was increased. Trees have taken water from ground and affected their quality by acidification and nitrification

process.

{Hong, 2018} Soil pH has been affecting our terrestrial ecosystem structure and function. Near about 549 sites were selected for afforestation and this has increased the carbon sequestration, water and soil. The output was indicated that afforestation can increased soil pH and also its fertility if tree species and initial pH were matched.

{, 2002} Soil organic carbon was affected by afforestation of farmer arable land with Oak and Norway spruce. Mineral soil carbon stored in 0-25 cm was decreased over the 29 years. The fertilized soil of afforestation was greater sinks for C.

{International, 2000} The "third generation international law" was not followed by people that cause the tropical and serious problem like deforestation and in interest in planation. The purpose of this institute was to inform the issues to people globally and obstructs the progress on forest conservation. In this agreement, there were many number of tumbler trees were grown and made organization that gave certificate for greenery program and manage their forest in a sustainable fashion.

3. Material and Method

Figure 2: Methodology Flowchart

Various conventional methods are accessible for data collection from the forest fields. Taking out block-level information is contemplate most commonly used due to its accuracy of more than 90% but it is a laborious, time-consuming, cost-effective, and hectic method. Large numbers of laborers required for this type of methodology may lead to considerable errors. Therefore, we used remotely sensed datasets of Landsat-5 and Sentinel-2 to estimate deforestation in the investigation site.

Table 1: Dates of satellite image acquisition

Sr.no	Platform	Date of acquisition	Resolution
1	Landsat-5	Oct 28, 2000	30m
2	Sentinel-2	Oct 17, 2020	10m, 20m

Spectral responses captured by spectral bands in red and near-infrared wavelength are very useful to estimate the health, growth and finally, production of forests have proved by various researchers. Moreover, these responses are used to compute vegetation indices including Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). These indices are very useful to differentiate the vegetative content existing in an investigation area compare to non-vegetation.

For the detection of vegetation in the satellite image and defined ranges for all land use features existing in the study area, NDVI was used for this. NDVI can be estimated by using the following formula.

$$NDVI = (NIR - RED) / (NIR + RED)$$

Where NIR is near-infrared

Vegetation response is captured maximum in NIR and minimum in red wavelength.

3.1 Supervised Classification

To check the reliability of NDVI based classification we executed supervised classification in Erdas Imagine 14 on the stack satellite image. A field survey was conducted using GPS to select samples from some remote locations which were not easily detectable on the satellite image with the naked eye.

3.2 Accuracy Assessment through Kappa Coefficients

We executed ground validation by creating a relationship between the supervised map and the real-time google earth imagery for accuracy assessment of supervised classification. To estimate the accuracy index Kappa Coefficient was used. A relationship established between classified map features to actual ground reality in the Kappa Coefficient.

To check the features is existing on the ground or not, the features are marked with a pinpoint on the classified map in this process. Multiple pinpoints are marked to find out the correct locations in comparison to misleading in this way. It is also called the accuracy of the expert, which can be expressed by the following formula:

$$Accuracy = (CPs / TPs) \times 100$$

Where CPs and TPs are corrected and total points respectively. Kappa Coefficient can be estimated using the following expression.

$$Kappa = ([TPs * CPs] - [Col * Rows]) / (TPs2 - [Col * Rows]) * 100$$

For the calculation of the Kappa Coefficient, all the input elements are rows and columns. E.g. the input figures for vegetative and non-vegetative area are as below in Table 2.

Table 2: A brief description of Kappa Coefficient in rows and columns

Class	Vegetated	Non-Vegetated	Total (User)
Vegetated	Corrected	Wrong	=Corrected+Wrong
Non-Vegetated	Wrong	Corrected	=Wrong+Corrected
Total Producer	=Corrected+Wrong	=Wrong+Corrected	Total of Samples

Values <0 as indicating no agreement and 0.01 to 0.20 as none to slight, 0.21 to 0.40 as fair, 0.41 to 0.60 as Moderate, 0.61 to 0.80 as substantial and 0.81 to 1.00 as almost perfect agreement. NDVI based classification of vegetated and non-vegetated is mentioned in the Table 3. These values were obtained by field visits during

the cross validation. Table 3 shows that vegetation returned maximum NDVI of 0.2-1.0 in comparison to Non-vegetation.

Table 3: NDVI based spectral responses of Vegetation and Non-Vegetation

Sr. No	Land Cover	NDVI Value
1	Non-Vegetation	-1-0.199
2	Vegetation	0.2-1.0

The spectral responses of vegetation and non-vegetation in below figure 3.

Figure 3: Spectral responses of vegetation and non-vegetation

4. Results and Discussions

NDVI based spatial distribution of features helped us to differentiate the vegetative and non-vegetated area. The NDVI based maps were generated for the years 2000 and 2020 to estimate the temporal changes in vegetation. Supervised classification of these images results in growth of vegetation. Classified map of year 2000 is shown in the Figure 4.

Figure 4 represents that the total area of Gatwala Park was 1,296,900 Square meter. It describes that 56.97% area was vegetative in 2000 in comparison to non-vegetative area 43.02%.

Vegetation Identification of Gatwala (Faisalabad District) - 2000

Figure 4: Classified map of Gatwala Park obtained using Landsat-5 image 2000.

For accuracy assessment, 33 sample point were obtained on the classified image of 2000 including 16 vegetated and 12 non-vegetated classes as mentioned in Table 4. We found five classes marked wrong among total 33 classes for the both vegetated and non-vegetated classes and calculated the value of Kappa coefficient as $K=0.69$. This value of K represents a good accuracy as described in methodology section.

Table 4: Accuracy assessment in the classified map of 2000.

Class	Vegetation	Non-vegetation	Total(User)
vegetation	16	4	20
Non-vegetation	1	12	13
Producer(Total)	17	16	33

Figure 5 Shows that the vegetative land cover increase from 56.97% to 62.01 within a temporal window of twenty years and the non-vegetative landcover decreased from 43.02% to 37.99% in same duration. Major transformation of vegetative area into barren land that increase the vegetation was 56.97% to 62.01. The vegetation landcover by 5%.

Vegetation Identification of Gatwala (Faisalabad District) - 2020

Figure 5: Classified map of Gatwala Park obtained using Sentinel-2 image 2020.

To determine the accuracy of classified map, we selected 42 points including 24 from vegetative area and 17 from non-vegetative area as described in the Table 5. One point was observed wrong while in cross validation of vegetative area and no point in case of non-vegetative area. In this case, Kappa coefficient was calculated as 97% accuracy. The value of $K=95$.

Table 5: Accuracy assessment in the classified map of 2020.

Class	Vegetation	Non-vegetation	Total(User)
vegetation	24	1	25
Non-vegetation	0	17	17
Producer(Total)	24	18	42

Discussion

This study describes a detailed methodology to estimate afforestation in Gatwala Forest Park. Results indicates about afforestation in this study area during 2000-2020 as described in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: Percentage of forest and non-forest areas from 2000-2020

Kappa coefficient performed well to access accuracy of classified imagery which was maximum for the classified imagery which was maximum for the classified map obtained using Sentinel-2 dataset, therefore, Sentinel-2 imagery was proved more reliable in comparison to Landsat imagery. The spectral responses of various land use classes were also mapped which are useful for other researches to recognize features through Remote Sensing. Results proved the sincere efforts of Pakistan government of vegetated landcover. The coverage of Billion tree Thusanami must be enhanced for increasing vegetation for a green Pakistan.

Figure 7: Analytical Map of Vegetation Identification

5. Summary

With the increased adverse effects of global warming, climate change and extreme weathers, the world is gathering on one point agenda which is increase in green land portion of the planet earth to avoid catastrophic future of the mankind. For this purpose, UN has already established the year 2011 as the year of forest.

Increased population, demand of the timber and its price and livelihood of millions of people connected with the forests has significantly decreased the green area of the land. Thirty percent of the total land area of the earth is covered with the forests and every year, the forest land mass of 75,625 Km² is decreased which has not only increased the temperature of the earth but also the weather conditions has become more unpredictable and unscheduled.

Pakistan is among world's top ten countries which are severely affected by the global warming. Even though that Pakistan is not contributing to the global warming to that extent but due to the geography of the land it is facing worse effects of the global warming. Pakistan has less than 5% of the total land covered with forests and deforestation in Pakistan was second highest in 1990 as per government resources. However, it is claimed by the government that forests have been increased progressively due to afforestation in 2010. However, in some other reports the forests have been decreased up to 2.2% during 2000-2012 in Pakistan which is an alarming situation. To avoid the upcoming challenges of the global warming, the only solution is to increase the forest land mass of the planet and especially Pakistan which is termed as afforestation. By increasing the forest and adopting the afforestation, the government can not only avoid the bad climate of the Pakistan but also the livelihood of millions of the people connected with the forests can also be saved.

In this project report, the idea of the afforestation is improvised to analyze the effects and other ecological aspects of this presented idea. For this purpose, a land area of the Faisalabad, Pakistan is taken as area of interest / study (AOI / S). This area is called "Gatwala Forest Park" which is 17Km on Faisalabad to Sheikhupura Road and 120Km away from Lahore, Pakistan. The geographic coordinates of the park are taken from on-site reference and fed to the ArcGIS 10.5 and Erdas Imagine 15 software for further analysis. On the other hand, Landsat-5 and Sentinel-2 images for different years (2000 & 2020) respectively are taken for further reference of the particular location. These two input values coming from on-site coordinates and above said satellites are further analyzed through supervised classification to further enhance the accuracy of the AOI. After the supervised classification the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) technique is utilized to check the green land of the AOI. Here, the vegetation index and green land are associated with the forests. The total land mass of the AOI is compared with the total land mass of the forest to find the actual percentage of the forests at Gatwala Forest Park. The analysis is based on the comparison between two NDVI values. One NDVI statistics are based on the data / imagery taken from Landsat-5 in 2000 while the other NDVI stats are based on the data / imagery taken from Sentinel-2 in 2020. Both these images after NDVI processing in ArcGIS gave the value of vegetation index / green land mass / forestation in "Gatwala Forest Park". The comparison between these two values gave an increased in vegetation index which leads to the increased forestation or afforestation in "Gatwala Forest Park".

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study used Landsat-5 (2000) and Sentinel-2 (2020) satellite imagery to estimate afforestation changes in Gatwala Forest Park, Faisalabad. Through supervised classification, NDVI analysis, and Kappa coefficient accuracy assessment, the results clearly show net afforestation over the 20-year period.

- Vegetation/forest cover increased from "56.97%" in 2000 to "62.01%" in 2020.
- Non-vegetated areas decreased from "43.02%" to "37.99%".
- Sentinel-2 imagery proved more reliable than Landsat-5 due to higher resolution and better classification accuracy (higher Kappa values).
- Spectral responses effectively separated vegetation from non-vegetation classes.

These findings highlight the successful efforts of the Ministry of Forestry (now Punjab Forests, Wildlife & Fisheries Department) in promoting tree plantation and protected area management. Despite Pakistan's overall low forest cover (around 2-5%) and past deforestation pressures, this local increase contributes to carbon sequestration, soil protection, better air quality in Faisalabad, and environmental sustainability.

The study confirms that remote sensing and GIS are powerful, cost-effective tools for monitoring land cover changes.

Recommendations

1. **Scale Up Plantation Efforts:** The Punjab Government should expand afforestation programs (e.g., under Green Pakistan Initiative and ongoing monsoon/spring campaigns) in areas like Gatwala Forest Park to further boost forest density and combat urban pollution.
2. **Use Better Technology for Monitoring:** Prioritize high-resolution Sentinel-2 (or newer) data for future studies, with regular change detection using NDVI and accuracy checks.
3. **Involve Communities and Policies:** Engage local people in tree care to improve survival rates, strengthen anti-encroachment laws, and promote eco-tourism in the park.
4. **Address Related Issues:** Reduce industrial pollution and urban expansion impacts on forest health in Faisalabad.
5. **Future Research:** Extend analysis beyond 2020 with recent satellite data to evaluate post-2020 plantation impacts (e.g., from national/provincial drives).

In summary, the rise in vegetation at Gatwala Forest Park is positive proof that targeted efforts work. Continued government action and monitoring can help Pakistan achieve greener landscapes and climate resilience.

References

- FAO (2010) Global forest resources assessment- 2010. FAO forestry paper No.163. UN Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome. pp85-146. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i1757e.pdf> (Accessed on 6 April 2016)
- Ahmad, S. S., Abbasi, Q., Jabeen, R., & Shah, M. T. J. P. J. B. (2012). Decline of conifer forest cover in Pakistan: a GIS approach. 44(2), 511-514.
- Anwar Ali 1, S. U., Shaiza Bushra 2, Naveed Ahmad 2*, Asad Ali 3, Muhmmad Awais Khan (2018).
- Arekhi, M. J. A. j. o. b. (2011). Modeling spatial pattern of deforestation using GIS and logistic regression: A case study of northern Ilam forests, Ilam province, Iran. 10(72), 16236-16249.
- Dania Amjad1, S. K., Faiza Sarwar. (2019).
- Faiza, N., Weiguo, J., Aijun, Y., & Wenxing, S. J. J. A. P. S. (2017). Giant deforestation leads to drastic eco-environmental devastating effects since 2000; a case study of Pakistan. 27(4), 1366-1376.
- KHAN, K. I., J.1 -ALI, A.2 -KHAN, S. N.1. (2019). doi:10.15666/aecer/1801_783815
- Owais, S. M., Siddiqui, S. J. I. J. o. E., & Geology, E. (2019). Appraisal of Deforestation and Forest Degradation in District Swat, Pakistan. 10(3), 7-15.
- Qamer, F. M., Abbas, S., Saleem, R., Shehzad, K., Ali, H., & Gilani, H. J. J. o. M. S. (2012). Forest cover change assessment in conflict-affected areas of northwest Pakistan: The case of Swat and Shangla districts. 9(3), 297-306.
- Qasim, M., Hubacek, K., Termansen, M., & Khan, A. J. A. G. (2011). Spatial and temporal dynamics of land use pattern in District Swat, Hindu Kush Himalayan region of Pakistan. 31(2), 820-828.
- Sajjad, A., Hussain, A., Wahab, U., Adnan, S., Ali, S., Ahmad, Z., & Ali, A. J. A. J. o. P. S. (2015). Application of remote sensing and GIS in forest cover change in Tehsil Barawal, District Dir, Pakistan. 6(09), 1501.
- N. Zaib un Nisa1, Kamran Mir2, 3*, Hina Fatimah, Syeda Maleeha, & Batool2, S., Salman Atif2 and Muhammad Arshad Awan3. (2018).
- O. Aljerf, L. J. B. I. J. (2017). "Biodiversity is Key for more variety for better society." 1(1): 00002.
- Bhatt, C. P. J. E. and Urbanization (1990). "The Chipko Andolan: forest conservation based on people's power." 2(1): 7-18.
- Huang, S. K., et al. (2016). "The applicability of marginal abatement cost approach: A comprehensive review." 127: 59-71.
- Lin, Y., et al. (2019). "The effects of urbanization on China's forest loss from 2000 to 2012: Evidence from a panel analysis." 214: 270-278.
- Rauf, T., et al. (2019). "Poverty and Prosperity: Impact on Livelihood Assets of Billion Trees Afforestation Program in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan." 10(10): 916.
- Xie, H., et al. (2017). "Exploring the factors influencing ecological land change for China's Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei Region using big data." 142: 677-687.
- Zhang, C., et al. (2015). "Disturbance-induced reduction of biomass carbon sinks of China's forests in recent years." 10(11): 114021.
- T. R. 1 et al. (2019). doi:10.3390/f10100916
- X. Z. 1 et al. (2018). doi:10.3390/w10121710
- *Hakim Shah, D. M. W. M., **Muhammad Afrasiyab, *** Dr. Javed Iqbal. (2010). Spatial Assessment of FSQ for Afforestation Using MCDA.
- Arshad Ashraf1, Muhammad Khubaib Abuzar2, B. A., & Muhammad Munir Ahmad, a. Q. H. (2017). Modeling Risk of Soil Erosion in High and Medium Rainfall Zones of Pothwar Region Pakistan.
- Asif Kamall, Ma Yingjie1, *, Ahmad Ali2. (2019). International Journal of Law and Society. doi:10.11648/j.ijls.20180104.13

- Berki, I., Bidlo, A., Druszler, A., Eredics, A., Galos, B., Matyas, C., ... Rasztoivits, E. (2013). Afforestation For Restoration Of Land And Climate Change.
- Danijel Belusic, R. F.-F., Gustav Strandberg and Alex Jukimenko. (2019). doi:10.1088/1748-9326/ab23b2
- G. A.Thivakaran. (2017). Wetland Science. doi:10.1007/978-81-322-3715-0_26
- H. Hussain, G. R. A. (2015). Sustainable Food Security in the Mountains of Pakistan Towards a Policy Framework. doi:10.1080/03670244.2015.1052426
- I. IBRAHIM*, K. M., & MUHAMMAD**, S. I. (2015).
- KATHLEEN A. FARLEY *w, E. G. J. G. Y. w. z. a. R. O. B. E. R. T. B. J. A. C. K. S. O. N. w. (2005). Global Change Biology (2005) 11, 1565-1576. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2486.2005.01011.x
- Keiffer, D. C. H. (1999).
- Kharl1, S., & X. X. (2017).
- Lacombel, G., et al. (2015). Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci. Discuss., 12, 12615-12648, 2015. doi:10.5194/hessd-12-12615-2015
- Maria Nijnik, A. O., 2 and Anatoliy Nijnik3. (2011). doi:10.1155/2012/295414
- Maria Nijnika, Pradipta Halder b. (2012). doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.08.014
- NAZIR1*, N., FAROOQ2, A., JAN1, S. A., & AHMAD3, A. (2019). J. Mt. Sci. (2019) 16(11): 2640-2653. doi:10.1007/s11629-018-5076-1
- OMER, A. A. O. (2010).
- OWOEYE1, I., O. O., & NJUGUNA2, a. P. (2019).
- Qazi, A. (2016).
- Sarah Waseem, U. K. (2019). Journal of Cleaner Production. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.06.228
- Suhadiyah1, S., J. S., P., R. B., & S. S. (2014).
- ULLAH, I. S., A.1 -ANSARI, L.1 -ALI, N.2 -AHMAD, N.1 -DAR, N. M.3 -DIN, N. U.3. (2018). doi:10.15666/aecr/1802_20572072
- Waqar Ahmad, A. U. K., 2), *, F. A. K., Muhammad Farooq2), Ammar Ahmad Baig2), & Liaqat Ali Shah2), J. K. (2020). doi:10.5572/ajae.2020.14.2.133
- Yahya Kooch, a. S. M. H., b Claudio Zaccone, Hamid Jalilvandc and Seyed Mohammad Hojjatic. (2012). Journal of Environmental Monitoring. doi:10.1039/c2em30410d.
- Yue Li, S. P., Laurent Z. X. Li, Anping Chen, Xuhui Wang, Philippe Ciais, & Ling Huang, X. L., Shushi Peng, Zhenzhong Zeng, Kai Wang, Liming Zhou. (2018). ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE.